

Exprimtent A:	Label-free mass spectrometry quantification (5 peptides per protein) of Nups and main associated proteins within affinity-purified isolated NPCs between wild type and the Δ FG NPC mutant. Supplemental Figure 8b.			
	Bio. Rep.	Δ FG	Bio. Rep.	Control
	1	Javi-Mlp1NPC-FG-Del-1-20210209	1	Javi-Mlp1NPC-WT-1-20210205
	2	Javi-Mlp1NPC-FG-Del-2-20210209	2	Javi-Mlp1NPC-WT-2-20210205
	3	Javi-Mlp1NPC-FG-Del-3-20210209	3	Javi-Mlp1NPC-WT-3-20210205
B:	Label-free mass spectrometry quantification (5 peptides per protein) of Nups and main associated proteins within affinity-purified isolated NPCs between wild type and the Nsp1FGx2 NPC mutant. Supplemental Figure 8c.			
	Bio. Rep.	Nsp1FGx2	Bio. Rep.	Control
	1	Trevor-NPC-2Nsp1-1-1-20230120	1	Trevor-NPC-WT1-1-20230113
	2	Trevor-NPC-2Nsp1-2-1-20230123	2	Trevor-NPC-WT2-1-20230117
	3	Trevor-NPC-2Nsp1-3-1-20230125	3	Trevor-NPC-WT3-1-20230118
C:	Label-free mass spectrometry quantification (5 peptides per protein) of proteins associated with affinity-purified isolated yeast NPCs (2 biological replicas). Data was collected at time 0 (immediately after isolation) or after the NPCs were incubated at 4°C (refrigerated) or snap-frozen in liquid nitrogen and stored at -80°C (frozen) for the indicated amount of time (in days). Figure 1i.			
# of days in storage	Bio. Rep.			
0	1	Javi-NPC-timecrs-1A-20220707		
	2	Javi-NPC-timecrs-2A-20220712		
	Bio. Rep.	Frozen	Bio. Rep.	Refrigerated
1	1	Javi-NPC-timecrs-1B-20220708	1	Javi-NPC-timecrs-1F-20220805
	2	Javi-NPC-timecrs-2B-20220708	2	Javi-NPC-timecrs-2F-20220808
3	1	Javi-NPC-timecrs-1C-20220713	1	Javi-NPC-timecrs-1G-20220809
	2	Javi-NPC-timecrs-2C-20220711	2	Javi-NPC-timecrs-2G-20220810
5	1	Javi-NPC-timecrs-1D-20220722	1	Javi-NPC-timecrs-1H-20220815
	2	Javi-NPC-timecrs-2D-20220727	2	Javi-NPC-timecrs-2H-20220812
7	1	Javi-NPC-timecrs-1E-20220802	1	Javi-NPC-timecrs-1I-20220816
	2	Javi-NPC-timecrs-2E-20220804	2	Javi-NPC-timecrs-2I-20220817